

DISTRIBUTION AND TAXONOMIC ISSUES OF PENDULINE TITS IN IRAN BASED ON ZARUDNY'S COLLECTIONS

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Abstract: According to the literatures, Zarudny's bird collection from Iran (Persia) is scattered in several museums all over the world. Taxonomy and biogeography of *Remiz* genus is in the shadow and there is no information on geographical distribution and systematic states of species in this taxon. It is turned out that about half of the collected individuals from this genus, *Remiz*, in Iran (67 of 135 samples based on registration number of all museums) are collected by Zarudny during his expeditions to Iran during 1898-1903. Zarudny almost a century ago based on a deep observation distinguished three species and seven subspecies for *Remiz* genus in Iran. The collected samples are deposited in different Museums in Europe and North America. Such as; Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (NMW), American Museum of Natural History (AMNH), Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences (ZISP), and Institute of Zoology of Uzbek Academy of Sciences (Tashkent Collection). The localities are provided with coordination and the historical distribution maps for members of this genus in Iran along some recommendations on the distribution and taxonomic situation of genus.

Keywords: Zarudny, *Remiz* genus, Historical map, Birds, Iran (Persia)

Introduction

Although Iran is based in arid and semiarid climatic zone, more than 150 rivers and 50 wetlands are listed in Iran (22 of them are as international registered wetlands) and these fresh water ecosystems have an important role in providing the breeding and wintering habitat of a large range of birds.

Among them penduline tits are highly depends on the fresh water ecosystems. This species despite having an extremely large range in Europe, its range in Iran only restricted to few localities and hence does approach the thresholds for vulnerable under the range size criterion

(extent of occurrence >20,000 km² combined with a declining or fluctuating range size, habitat extent/quality, or population size and a small number of locations or severe fragmentation). The population trend appears to be decreasing, because of removing built nests by local people. Penduline tits builds an elaborate hanging nest, which normally taken by local people to be used as children's toys or a decoration. There is no recent estimation of local populations but the population size is small, and approaches the thresholds for vulnerable under the population size criterion.

Remiz pendulinus complex (Sibley and Monroe 1990, 1993) has been split into *R. pendulinus* and *R. macronyx* following Harrap and Quinn (1996) who recognises four species of *Remiz*: *pendulinus*, *macronyx*, *coronatus* and *consobrinus*. These four species are treated as separate species owing to consistent morphological and ecological differences between them with habitat partitioning occurring where two taxa occur in sympatry. Eck and Martens (2006) lump *macronyx* with *pendulinus* citing hybridisation between them on the north and southwest shores of the Caspian Sea as a factor. Roselaar (in Dickinson 2003) favours treating this complex as three species; *R. pendulinus* (4 races), *R. macronyx* (5 races), and *R. coronatus* (3 races).

In this study we are going to trace the former localities and draft the historical collection map of penduline tits and show the observations and collections of Zarudny in Iran.

Pendulin tits

Penduline tits are tiny passerines that resemble the true tits (Family Paridae) and locate in a separate family, Remizidae. A penduline tit is a small, neat, well-patterned bird. It is usually close to water, although sometimes several fields away in lines of trees along little more than a ditch or beside a damp meadow. It is common

in southeast Europe, but spreading in the west, with increasing appearances in the UK in recent decades.

Distinctive high voice, far-carrying, pure whistle, *psieeee*, song simple mix of trills and calls. Remarkable hanging nest of plant down and cobwebs with tubular entrance high on side, dangling from slim twig; brood in a year during May–June. Eats small insects and reed seeds, in acrobatic tit-like manner. Flight is quick, erratic, bounding undulations with bursts of wingbeats. This species has an exceptionally diverse breeding system, in which both males and females may have up to 5–7 mates in a single breeding season, and the eggs are incubated by a single parent: either the male or the female (Mészáros et al., 2006).

Penduline tits in Iran

Penduline tits in Iran, based on examination of skins and literatures (Bochenski, 1998; Dolgushin et al., 1972; Stepanyan, 2003; Zarudny and Härms, 1912; Zarudny, 1892; Zarudny, 1908b), are comprises of 3 species with a total of 7 subspecies. Eurasian Penduline Tit (*Remiz pendulinus*), Black-headed Penduline Tit (*Remiz macronyx*), and White-crowned Penduline Tit (*Remiz coronatus*), all occurring in Iran. The subspecies that appear in Iran seems to be: *R. p. pendulinus*, *R. p. menzbieri*, *R. p. neglectus*, *R. p. caspius*, *R. m. macronyx*, *R. m. nigricans*, and *R. c. coronatus*. In Iran reliable recorded subspecies and their distribution are *R. p. menzbieri* (north-western Iran, Zagros Mountains), *R. p. caspius* (along the south-eastern shores of the Caspian Sea), *R. m. macronyx* (south Caspian), *R. m. nigricans* (Sistan basin), *R. c. coronatus* (north-eastern of Iran).

Though the review here based on recent investigations, Zarudny at 1911 reached already the same conclusion - almost a century ago - distinguishing 3 species with a total of 7 subspecies in Iran, though the names he used are deviating from those used at present.

Eurasian Penduline Tit *Remiz pendulinus*

The taxonomic status of *R. pendulinus* is more difficult to decide; it agrees in habitat and nest with *R. coronatus*, but overlaps with *R. macronyx* in the upper Yenisey valley (Russia) without mixed

pairings; on the other hand, despite difference in habitat and nest, *R. pendulinus* shows some local hybridization with *R. macronyx* in the SW corner of the Caspian Sea.

The most widespread form breeding in Iran is *R. pendulinus menzbieri*, originally described by Zarudny (1913a) from the lower Karun in Khuzestan and breeding in the west and south. In winter, some *R. p. pendulinus* from central and east European Russia, *R. p. caspius* from the north and west shore of the Caspian Sea and *R. p. jaxarticus* (possibly *Remiz pendulinajaxa* rtensissynonym of *R. p. pendulinus*) from north Kazakhstan and SW Siberia may appear in Iran.

White-crowned Penduline Tit *Remiz coronatus*

Many *R. coronatus* have been seen and at least 20 have been collected by Zarudny in Khorasan in late 1900 and in Baluchestan in early 1901 (Zarudny, 1916): Kariz 14 November, Hari-Rud valley near Pish-Robat 16 November (e.g. one in NMW Vienna), Rud-e Shur near Dastgerd 2 December, Chah-e Bani well 5 December (at least four birds now in AMNH), Bandan 10 December, Mir-Kuh 28 January, Khan Mohammad-Abad ('Ande') 29 January (at least 4 birds now in AMNH and NMW), Juankan 8 February (one in AMNH), Narreh-Now 9 February, Jalq 12 February (one in AMNH), Qaleh-Eybi 14 February (one in AMNH), MokSukhteh/Maksotag 16 February, Mirkala 17 February, Sarbaz 4 March (one in AMNH), and Gol-Posht and Rask 10–11 March (3 birds in AMNH). Out-of-season (or pointing to possible breeding?) are a female collected at Gunich near Bampur on 10 May 1901 (Zarudny, in AMNH) and a female from Esfahan on 28 April 1893 (NMW, collector unknown). Said to breed in Iran in the Hari-Rud valley (Zarudny, 1911), where several have been collected on the Afghan side of the river in late April 1885 by Aitchison (Sharpe 1889) and along the Tajan/Tedzhen where *R. coronatus* breeds at least on the Turkmenistan part of the river (Stepanyan, 2003).

The breeding range of *R. coronatus* overlaps widely with that of *R. macronyx* in westcentral Asia (e.g. Dolgushin et al., 1972), both differ distinctly in habitat favored and in build of

nest (Bochenski, 1998), and hence at least two species are involved. Much scarcer and locally extinct as breeder are the various subspecies or *R. macronyx* breeding in north and east Iran. *R. m. macronyx* and *R. c. coronatus* which breed from Turkmenistan north to south Kazakhstan occur in winter in Iran.

Black-headed Penduline Tit *Remiz macronyx*

The subspecies *neglectus* was very common in the Gorgan Bay marshes near Bandar-e Gaz on 6 July 1885, and Zarudny collected many adults, eggs, juveniles, etc (Zarudny 1892). This subspecies was originally described as '*loudoni*', based on a series of birds collected at Lankaran (Azerbaijan Republic), Gilan, Mazandaran, and Golestan, though details on numbers and localities have not been published (Zarudny, 1908b); as the name '*loudoni*' was already in use in *Remiz*, the name was later changed to *neglectus* (Zarudny, 1914), and because birds from Lankaran and Gilan appeared to be hybrid with *R. pendulinus caspius*, the type locality was restricted to Chat-e Atrek (Golestan) from where Zarudny had obtained 'new material' of the species (again without supplying further data); he examined also birds from Miankalehsandspit (Zarudny, 1914). The main difference between *neglectus* and nominate *macronyx* from further north in Transcaucasia is size (wing length *neglectus* 50–56 mm, *macronyx* 56–60.5 mm; tail length 45–48 (–51) mm and 51–56.5 mm respectively) (Zarudny, 1914). Shestoporov (1927) observed *neglectus* at Chat-e Atrek on 5 October 1916 and on the small lakes east of Gonbad-e Qabus from November 1916 to mid-January 1917. Other *neglectus* have been collected by Woosnam in Gohar-Baran (Farahabad) (Sari, Mazandaran) on 16 March 1907 (two females) and at Anzali Wetland (Gilan) on 20 May 1907 (male), wings 52, 53, 54 mm (Witherby, 1908) and by Koelz at Borujerd (Lorestan) on 6 September 1942 (male, in FMNH); whether two black-headed birds seen collecting nest-material at Anzali Wetland on 30 March 1963 were *neglectus* or hybrids with *R. p. caspius* is not sure. Outside Iran, *neglectus* has a rather small breeding range in southwest and south Turkmenistan, east to Merv oasis and the lower Tajan/Tedzhen and Murghabrivers. *R. macronyx nigricans* was a subspecies endemic

to the Sistan basin which now may be extinct. Zarudny collected many from 27 May to 3 June 1898 and in January and June 1901 in the basin, and these are now in various natural history collections (e.g. 12 birds in AMNH). The type series of *nigricans*, described by Zarudny (1908b), was based on birds collected 1898 in marshes along the Hamun-e Farah, Hamun-e Sabari, and near the Hirmand river mouth; some of his birds of 1901 came from Gaz-e Bar and Adimi in Sistan gives many details on plumages, nests, nesting biology, eggs, etc. of *nigricans*. Paludan (1959) observed and collected birds resembling *R. p. caspius* on the Afghan side of the Sistan basin (Farah-Rud delta, 8 March 1949, 2–3 km from Iran), but could not find *nigricans* in the largely waterless basin. Further *R. macronyx* and *R. coronatus* may have been among the many unidentified '*R. pendulinus*' recorded from Iran.

All three species are considered separate here, differing in colour of plumage, in relative length of reduced outermost primary, and in build of bill, leg, and foot (slender in *R. pendulinus* and *R. coronatus*, heavy in *R. macronyx*). There is not any comprehensive study on the species in recent years in Iran. About the morphology of these species only in some field guides it is mentioned briefly and I did not see any skin of them in Iranian museums. Finally there are three species: Eurasian Penduline Tit (*Remiz pendulinus*), Black-headed Penduline Tit (*Remiz macronyx*), and White-crowned Penduline Tit *Remiz p. coronatus* in Iran (Table 1).

Penduline tits collections in Minor Asia

The ornithological collection of National University of Uzbekistan in the Department of Vertebrate Zoology is a large scientific fund comprising 20,902 specimens of 606 species. The largest part of the collection (13,281 specimens) is comprised of collections made by the world-famous ornithologist Nikolai Alekseevich Zarudny during his travels in Iran and Turkestan. The Persian collections made by N. A. Zarudny, and partly by S. I. Bilkevich, constitute about 11% of this collection. The museum has a large collection of particularly passerines from all regions of Iran with all major taxa represented.

Table 1. Species and subspecies of *Remiz* and their geographic ranges in Iran

Eurasian Penduline Tit <i>(Remiz pendulinus)</i>	Black-headed Penduline Tit <i>(Remiz macronyx)</i>	White-crowned Penduline Tit <i>(Remiz coronatus)</i>
<i>R. p. menzbieri</i> (north-western Iran, Zagros Mountains), <i>R. p. caspius</i> (along the south-eastern shores of the Caspian Sea)	<i>R. m. macronyx</i> (south Caspian Sea), <i>R. m. nigricans</i> (Sistan basin)	<i>R. c. coronatus</i> (north-eastern of Iran)

Table 2. *Remizskins* in the ornithological collection of National University of Uzbekistan collected by Zarudny.

Species	Male (♂)	Female (♀)	Unidentified Sex (☼)	Total (Iran)	All Specimens (Iran And Others)
<i>Remiz pendulinus</i>	9	12	0	21	90 (46♂, 26♀, 18☼)
<i>Remiz coronatus</i>	0	0	0	0	4 (1♂, 0♀, 3☼)
<i>Remiz macronyx</i>	1	0	0	1	36 (17♂, 9♀, 10☼)

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Appendix

Genus *Remiz* Jarocki, 1819 based on check-list of birds of the world (Peters, 1967), synonyms and their distribution in paleacretic region. Type, by monotypy, *Remiz pendulinus* Cuvier = *Motacilla pendulinus* Linnaeus. *Remiz pendulinus* is composed of *Remiz pendulinus pendulinus* (Linnaeus), *Remiz pendulinus caspius* (Pelzam), *Remiz pendulinus coronatus* (Severtzov), *Remiz pendulinus macronyx* (Severtzov), *Remiz pendulinus nigricans* (Zarudny), *Remiz pendulinus stoliczkae* (Hume), and *Remiz pendulinus consobrinus* (Swinhoe).

***Remiz pendulinus pendulinus* (Linnaeus)**

Motacilla pendulinus Linnaeus, 1758.

Remiz apendulina jaxartensis Sushkin, 1904.

Anthoscopus ssaposhnikowi Johansen, 1907.

Remiz apendulina bostanjogli Zarudny, 1913.

Remiz apendulina menzbieri Zarudny, 1913.

Remiz amacronyx loudoni Zarudny, 1914.

Remiz amacronyx paradoxa Zarudny, 1914.

Anthoscopus pendulinus persimilis Hartert, 1918.

Remiz apendulinus barabensis Zarudny and Johansen, 1923.

Distribution: Southern and eastern Europe, western Siberia east to Semipalatinsk, Asia Minor, Mesopotamia, and southern and western Iran. Hybridizes locally in eastern parts of range with *macronyx* and *coronatus* (*ssaposhnikovi*, *bostanjogli*, *loudoni* and *paradoxa* are hybrid forms). This and other subspecies occur south of breeding range in winter.

Remiz pendulinus caspius (Pelzam)

Aegithalus caspius Pelzam, 1870.

Distribution: Lower Volga River and middle and lower Ural River, north and west coasts of Caspian Sea, and vicinity of Lake Balkash.

***Remiz pendulinus coronatus* (Severtzov)**

Aegithalus coronatus Severtzov, 1873.

Remiz ayeniseensis Sushkin, 1904.

Distribution: Central Asia and southern Siberia, from lower Amu-Darya and Syr-Darya in the west to East Sayan Mountains and upper Yenisei in the east. Hybridizes locally with *pendulinus* in north of range.

***Remiz pendulinus macronyx* (Severtzov)**

Aegithalus macronyx Severtzov, 1873.

Anthoscopus rutilans neglectus Zarudny, 1908.

Remiz amacronyx aralensis Zarudny, 1916.

Distribution: West-central Asia, from eastern Transcaucasia through northern Iran and Turkmenia (Atrek Basin) to Aral Sea, and east to Ferghana and the lower Hi. Hybridizes locally with *pendulinus*.

***Remiz pendulinus nigricans* (Zarudny)**

Anthoscopus rutilans nigricans Zarudny, 1908.

Distribution: Seistan, eastern Iran.

***Remiz pendulinus stoliczkae* (Hume)**

Aegithalus Stoliczkae Hume, 1874.

Remiz apendulina centralasiae Sushkin, 1904.

Distribution: Eastern Turkestan, northern Mongolia, southern Transbaikalia, and middle Amur Valley.

***Remiz pendulinus consobrinus* (Swinhoe)**

Aegithalus consobrinus Swinhoe, 1870

Remiz consobrinus suffusus Clark, 1907.

R[emiz] c[onsobrinus] japonicus Clark, 1907.

Distribution: Manchuria and eastern and northeastern China. Straggler to southern Korea and Japan.